

PHONETIC EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATION IN CHILDREN'S SPEECH

Kurbanova Munavvara Abdujabbarovna

Professor of Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, doctor of philology

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Abstract. *The article highlights the pragmatic nature of the phenomenon of connotation and highlights the specific features of children's speech. In the process of communication, children try to increase the impact and emotionality of speech by lengthening the vowel sound in the lexical unit, doubling the consonant sound, pronouncing the words into syllables. In the speech of preschool children, the connotative meaning expressed in the form of short repetition creates emphasis and serves to ensure effectiveness, the cases of distorted pronunciation of the sounds in the proper words or the inability to say a certain sound attract the attention of the addressee. It is said that it acquires an important pragmatic feature.*

Keywords: *connotation, children's speech, context, pragmalinguistics, communicative purpose, denotative meaning, sound, syllable, stress, phonetic process.*

INTRODUCTION: In the process of reflecting the external world through language, a person cannot ignore his feelings, experiences, and his attitude to reality. In this process, the owner of the language adds additional meaning and shades of meaning to the linguistic units. In linguistics, the additional meanings and shades of meaning that accompany language units are collectively known as connotation.

Connotation in a narrow sense reflects the expressive-emotional possibilities of language in practical use. The emergence of connotation in the process of practical use of the language in connection with the subject of speech, its connection with the context shows that it is a research object of pragmalinguistics. In the works carried out in this direction, the linguistic nature of this phenomenon, which serves to increase speech effectiveness, expressive-emotionality, colorfulness in connection with the communicative goal of the speaker, was revealed, and its semantic types were distinguished. [1, 83; 2, 69-74; 3, 143; 4, 3-9; 5, 30-35; 6, 21-30; 7, 156-174; 8, 62-71; 9, 271; 10, 152; 11, 3-9] In this, the main attention was paid to the analysis of issues such as ways of connotative meaning expression in speech, verbal and non-verbal units forming connotation, their role in creating expressive-emotionality in the text. The traditional interpretation of connotation, i.e. the expression of expressive-emotional nature of language units (emotional connotation) was also expressed in the modern interpretation in an emotional-evaluative way.

In the research conducted in the last century, it was observed that the border of connotation has expanded even more. In the context of connotation, socio-political, moral-ethical, ethnographic concepts reflected in the language were also studied. arose on the basis of the tendency to determine the structure of meaning.

Phonetic units have a special place in the expression of speech connotation. In A. Haydarov's research, the inherent (internal) and adherent (external, speech) forms of connotation realized through phonetic means in the Uzbek language are distinguished, inherent connotation is based on segmental phonetic elements, and adherent connotation is based on supersegmental phonetic phenomena. Also, in the work, the emergence of connotation based on prolonged

pronunciation of vowels and doubling of consonants is highlighted through evidentiary examples. Emphasis, intonation, pause as its component and a number of connotatives such as joy, admiration, begging, supplication, approval, displeasure, humiliation, pity, anger, recitation through syllable pronunciation the formation of meanings is shown. [13, 21]

In S.Makhsuimova's research on the issue of the expression of connotation in the artistic text, the famous Uzbek poet E.Vahidov's creation of connotation in the poetic text and the pragmatic purpose of it, the ways of expressing the connotation in the artistic text, and the poetic tools that create the connotation are deeply discussed. studied. In the research, the connotative meaning in E.Vahidov's poems is phonetically used: a) to pronounce the vowel strongly, that is, to exaggerate the meaning with the help of percussive stress; b) lengthening the vowel, that is, strengthening the meaning by means of quantitative emphasis; c) folding the consonant; g) methods of achieving the effectiveness of the text through sound replacement, as well as alliteration and contamination are shown. In E. Vahidov's poetry, it is explained on the basis of examples that playfulness, musicality, and impressiveness of expression are provided in the text through syntactic devices, specific repetition of impulses and words, and intertextuality. [14, 21] The phenomenon of connotation reflects the specific aspects of children's speech. In the process of speech, they use the methods of expressing connotative meaning in the same way as adults in the process of performing speech actions, such as informing about reality, expressing a question about reality unknown to them, encouraging the listener to perform an action. Therefore, the connotation specific to children also occurs in the speech process.

MAIN PART. In children's speech, different phonetic processes occur in the structure of words. The following phonetic phenomena observed in the speech of preschool children serve for the expression of connotation:

1. Pronunciation of a vowel sound. During the speech process, children try to increase the impact of speech by elongating the vowel sound in the word. For example:

"Sister, were you polite in kindergarten?"

- *Of course.*

- *Did you study well?*

- *Of course!*

"If not, why haven't you been able to get me a toy car with remote control since wheeeeeen?" (U. Hoshimov. "Inscriptions of the notebook")

It is characteristic that the lengthening of a vowel in a word occurs in different syllables of the word. Compare:

1. - Hey, tell me about you.

- That's it, sleep...

- Just teeeeeell me.

- Okay, listen. Once there is, once there is no. Once upon a time there was a young man...

- Well... When I grow up, will I go to the cities?

- You will go, my son, you will go. (U. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")

2. In an instant, darkness covered everything... My heart was filled with panic. Hey! - I said crying. (O'. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")

3. "No," I begged. - Dad, no. (U. Hoshimov. "Between Two Doors")

2. Consonant doubling. This phonetic phenomenon observed in speech is referred to in the sources as "double consonant", "double consonant", "double consonant", "gemination", "folding

of consonants". [13] The essence of this phenomenon is that, based on a specific pragmatic purpose, one consonant in the word is doubled, that is, it is brought to the double consonant position in pronunciation. As a result, the meaning of the word is exaggerated and the effectiveness of the speech increases. [15, 11]

Children also try to convey the idea effectively by doubling the consonant sound in the word. Our observations show that children try to exaggerate the meaning of these words by doubling the consonants *z* and *s* in the words *maza* and *rosa*. This situation creates a speech connotation. For example:

Oh, I wish my wedding would be sooner. I wore my new dress, my new cap, and my boots with pistons, and I was playing with fun! (Kh.Tokhtaboev. "Paradise people")
- I got a lot of high fives today. (Abdullah Mutalov, 7 years old)

While thinking about the doubling of consonants, A.Haydarov stated the following: "The lengthening of consonants is realized by pronouncing them in a double consonant position in oral speech, and by writing them in double consonants in written speech." [12, 10] Note that the doubling of consonants is defined on the basis of length. In our opinion, the doubling of the consonant is not related to the "lengthening" of the sound, but to its increase.

In the following examples, a specific connotation is created by the child based on the doubling of the consonant sound: At one end, our "bird's head" gets mixed with mud while playing, and the ball "falls away" is also crooked. (U. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")

In the Uzbek language, the doubling of consonants has occurred, and this situation creates a connotative meaning through some lexical units that have become fixed in the word structure. Such units used by children also create speech effectiveness. For example:

I came back in a hurry. (U. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")
... At one point, I stopped at the top as if I had seen a miracle. (U. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")

3. Pronunciation of the word by dividing it into syllables. Children can increase the impact and emotionality of speech based on the pronunciation of words divided into syllables during the speech process. According to A. Haydarov, "an additional connotative meaning emerges when a strong pressure (emphasis) is placed on the syllables of the word separated by short pauses." [13, 15]

When saying a word with syllables, additional meanings such as emphasis, determination, objection appear. For example, in the speech of Abdulbasit Abdujabbarov (age 3), who speaks the dialect of the city of Tashkent, observing the expression of connotative meanings such as children's firmness and objection in the sentence "Ux-la-miy-man" in relation to the note that his mother reminded him of the need to sleep possible

According to A. Haydarov, the words pronounced in syllables have the meaning of urgency and determination related to performing or not performing an action. (*o'-qiy-san, bor-may-man*) excess of the norm, strength of the sign (*qip-qizil, sap-sariq, ko'm-ko'k*), strong expression of intensity, emphasis, etc (*qi-ip-qizil, ko'-o'm-ko'k, qo-op-qora*) such connotative meanings are formed. [13, 15] In our opinion, *qip-qizil, sap-sariq, ko'm-ko'k* it is not very correct to evaluate the method of creating the meaning of the sign's excess and strength in adjectives by the way of pronouncing the word by syllables. Because as *qizil qi – zil, sariq as sa – riq* It is not pronounced in syllables. *Ko'k* quality is not even divided into syllables. Also *qi-ip-qizil, ko'-o'm-ko'k, qo-op-qora* syllables are not pronounced in adjectives either. In our opinion, it is appropriate to talk about

the combination of sounds in the structure of the word in a way that corresponds to the pronunciation. Because in word *qizil ip* or in word *ko 'k o 'm, qora op* not a syllable of these words.

4. Repeating and phonetically changing the syllable. Connotation is also expressed through short repetition in the speech of preschool children. In this process, a phonetic change occurs in the structure of the word. In this case, the first syllable of the word is repeated in front of the word using appropriate sounds p, m, s, which help to connect it with the next syllable. For example:

The star's sister gave him a very beautiful napkin. The star was happy:

"Sister, is this kiss for me?" - he said. (M. Sodikova. "She is sweet, so are her words")

It seems that the child formed a connotative meaning in his speech by the method of short repetition. Such a repeated emphasis brought to the surface and ensured effectiveness. It is characteristic that the expression of connotation in this way is mainly characteristic of the speech of preschool children.

Some linguists note that the form of the accretive degree in adjectives is formed phonetically, and that the sound at the end of the acquired part before the word consists mainly of explosive m, p sounds. [16, 55-58; 17, 15] For example, red and green. However, in children's speech, it is observed that not only adjectives, but also morphological units belonging to other categories create connotative meaning in this way. The above example also confirms our opinion.

5. Phonetically distorted pronunciation of the sounds in the word. Abnormal situations observed in the process of children's pronunciation of sounds, although this situation creates a pragmatic obstacle in speech, sometimes serves for connotation. Especially in the speech of children of preschool age, the distorted pronunciation of the sounds in the acquired words or the inability to say a certain sound acquires an important pragmatic feature in attracting the addressee's attention. For example:

The boy was still screaming and crying: - Give me a warm blanket! (U. Hoshimov. "Works of the World")

I hate boots, shoes are better than them, if you untie them like this or that, they come off. (Kh. Tokhtaboev. "Paradise people")

- I... I agree with everything you say. You're late, my dear, you're late! (P. Kadirov. "Adventures of Akram")

- Oijon, be late! (Dilnoza Choreva, 2 years old)

From the analysis of the examples, it is known that the formation of connotation by phonetic method in the speech of children compared to adults is somewhat diverse and widespread.

CONCLUSION. So, in the realization of connotation, among other factors such as the speaker's linguistic reserve, knowledge of the language and the ability to use it, of course, age also plays an important role. A bright, unique expression of connotation is manifested in children's speech. Today, one of the urgent tasks of Uzbek pragmalinguistics is to study such issues as the expression of connotation in children's speech, its types, the place and importance of connotation in the text in a monographic aspect.

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